

The two glutinous rice varieties Black Puttu and White Puttu, both with tall plant stature, recorded 2.5 and 1.7 t/ha, respectively (see table). Both Jeeraga Samba types are characterized by low rough rice weight and moderate yield

potential. Dwarf-statured, nonlodging varieties IET8580 (Kasthuri) and IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1) have brown rice, length of more than 7 mm, and an L:B ratio of about 4. They possess good yield potential. IET8580 is strongly

scented; IET10364 is lightly scented.

The superiority of Pusa Basmati 1 was revealed in this study. It is being used as donor in the breeding program to improve aromatic and quality rice varieties in Tamil Nadu. □

Performance of quality rice varieties at TRRI, Aduthurai, Tamil Nadu, India.

Variety	Pedigree	Duration (d)	Plant ht at maturity (cm)	Yield (t/ha)	1000-grain wt ^a (g)	Brown rice			Shape ^b	Scent ^c
						Length (mm)	Breadth (mm)	L:B		
Black Puttu	Local	134	131	2.5	21.2	6.9	2.0	3.5	S	0
White Puttu	Local	144	134	1.7	23.8	7.0	2.5	2.8	M	0
AEB148	Jeeraga Samba-nonscented	140	137	1.5	10.2	4.5	2.2	2.0	B	0
AEB178	Jeeraga Samba-scented	140	140	1.7	10.0	4.4	2.2	2.0	B	2
Sugadas	Local	142	142	2.0	21.0	6.7	2.7	2.5	M	1
Rascadam	Local	135	145	1.1	11.4	4.3	2.3	1.9	B	1
HBC19	Karnal Local	141	109	0.8	20.8	7.7	1.8	4.3	S	1
Basmati 370	Local	141	110	1.8	21.5	7.5	1.9	3.9	S	1
IET8580 (Kasthuri)	Basmati 370/CR88-17-1-5	139	103	1.9	20.8	7.3	1.9	3.8	S	1
IET10364 (Pusa Basmati 1)	Pusa 167/Karnal Local	134	88	2.4	18.4	7.4	1.8	4.1	S	2

^aRough rice basis. ^bS = slender, M = medium, B = bold. ^c0 = nonscented, 1 = lightly scented, 2 = scented. Based on SES.

Effect of plant density on rice grain quality

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We tested three levels of plant densities—118, 560, 160, 550, and 197,600 plants/ha—for Basmati 385 and advanced line 4048 during 1989-90 and 1990-91 cropping seasons. The experiment was laid out in a randomized complete block design with three replications in 4- × 6-m plots. Data were averaged.

Thousand-grain weight, cooked grain length, total milling recovery, head rice recovery, and protein content decreased as plant densities of both varieties

increased (see table). The effect of plant density on kernel dimension, amylose content, and gel length was not consistent. □

Effect of plant density on grain quality parameters, 1989-90, 1990-91.^a

Quality character	Basmati 385			Basmati line 4048		
	118,560	160,550	197,600	118,560	160,550	197,600
Grain length (mm)	6.75 a	6.74 a	6.72 a	7.28 a	7.29 a	7.19 b
Grain width (mm)	1.63 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.60 a	1.62 a	1.60 a
1000-grain wt (g)	15.02 a	14.84 a	14.69 a	16.28 a	16.11 b	15.41 c
Cooked grain length (mm)	13.50 a	13.30 b	13.10 c	13.95 a	13.75 a	13.45 b
Total milled rice (%)	70.40 a	70.00 a	69.60 a	70.30 a	69.80 a	69.00 b
Head rice (%)	54.60 a	53.00 ab	51.43 b	52.70 a	50.90 b	48.00 c
Bursting of grains upon cooking (%)	6.50 a	8.33 a	9.17 a	4.50 a	4.60 a	5.50 a
Protein content (%)	9.10 a	8.70 a	8.40 a	8.90 a	8.60 a	8.40 a
Amylose content (%)	25.00 a	24.90 a	24.90 a	23.70 b	23.70 b	24.90 a
Gel length (mm)	67.50 b	65.60 b	84.50 a	66.50 b	65.10 b	79.00 a

^aValues in a row followed by a common letter do not significantly differ at the 5% level by DMRT.

Comparison of grain quality of mechanically and hand-harvested rice

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Combine harvesters are becoming popular in Punjab, Pakistan, because of the shortage of farm labor during the peak harvest season.

From 15 locations in Sahiwal, Okara, and Kasur districts, we collected samples of KS282 (medium-grain) and Basmati

Grain quality of mechanically harvested and hand-harvested rice.^a

Character ^b	KS282		Basmati 198	
	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested	Mechanically harvested	Hand-harvested
Moisture content (%)	29.7 a	20.2 b	30.5 a	21.0 b
Green and immature grains (%)	11.2 a	4.0 b	14.1 a	6.2 b
Production of husked grains (%)	2.1 a	0.0 b	3.2 a	0.0 b
Total milling recovery (% db)	69.8 b	71.5 a	68.7 b	70.0 a
Head rice recovery (% db)	54.2 b	58.1 a	50.0 b	55.0 a

^aIn a row, values followed by the same letter for each variety are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT. ^bdb = dry basis.

198 (fine-grain) that were harvested with a Ford New Holland model 8040 combine harvester. A small portion of

the same fields was harvested and grains threshed by hand for comparison. Results were averaged across locations.

The presence of green, immature, and husked grains (brown rice) was significantly higher in mechanically harvested rice than in hand-harvested and threshed rice for both varieties (see

table). The higher moisture percentage in the combine-harvested rice is due to the larger amount of green and immature grains, which may be attributed to the superior threshing efficiency of the

combine harvester. Total milling and head rice recovery in combine-harvested rice were 1.3-1.7 and 3.9-5.0% lower, respectively, than those in hand-harvested rice. □

Grain quality of some promising medium-grain rices

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We compared the physicochemical characteristics of some promising

medium-grain rice breeding lines with standard varieties IR6 and KS282. Rices were grown under similar environmental conditions in yield trials during 1988-90.

Eight of the 14 lines approached the standard varieties in kernel length and length-breadth ratio. Head rice recovery was 49.2-57.4% (see table). Only PK1385-9-1-B-1-1 gave slightly higher head rice than KS282. Broken rice

among lines tested was 14.0-20.0%. Proportionate elongation on cooking of eight lines was at par with that of IR6 and KS282. None of the lines approached KS282 in protein content. All lines, as well as the standard varieties, had high amylose content and low gelatinization temperature (alkali spreading value of 6-7). Gel consistency values ranged from 32 to 64 mm. □

Physicochemical characteristics of some promising medium-grain lines.

Variety or line	Grain length (mm)	Grain breadth (mm)	Length-breadth ratio	Milling recovery		Proportionate elongation on cooking	Protein content (%)	Amylose content (%)	Alkali spreading value	Gel consistency (mm)
				Head rice (%)	Broken rice (%)					
PK1385-9-1-B-1-1	6.51	1.97	3.30	57.4	14.6	1.58	8.38	28.2	6.5	64
PK1385-9-1-B-1-12	6.51	1.95	3.34	55.7	14.0	1.63	9.00	28.2	6.4	47
PK1385-9-1-B-1-13	6.23	1.96	3.18	55.0	15.9	1.70	9.18	28.5	6.5	60
PK2480-7-3-1	6.62	1.76	3.76	55.3	16.0	1.70	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3303-7-2	6.85	1.82	3.76	54.6	15.5	1.60	8.64	28.0	6.6	53
PK3305-15-1	6.84	1.81	3.78	53.5	17.2	1.61	8.73	28.5	6.5	56
PK3327-13-1	6.28	1.97	3.19	55.1	15.0	1.72	8.02	27.5	6.5	55
PK3358-13-3-2	6.47	1.84	3.52	54.0	16.6	1.75	8.38	29.5	6.5	47
PK3717-9	6.79	1.84	3.69	54.7	16.1	1.73	8.02	28.7	6.2	45
PK3717-12	6.75	1.85	3.65	53.0	17.3	1.75	8.46	28.0	6.5	42
PK3727-2	6.72	1.85	3.63	53.8	17.0	1.71	8.02	28.0	6.4	50
PK3721-5	6.74	1.87	3.60	56.0	15.2	1.65	8.28	28.5	6.5	47
PK3817-33	6.80	1.86	3.65	55.5	15.7	1.71	8.02	27.2	6.3	40
PK3849-18	6.81	1.82	3.74	49.2	20.0	1.64	8.12	28.0	6.5	32
IR6	6.72	1.84	3.65	55.7	15.2	1.70	7.62	29.1	6.6	41
KS282	6.84	1.79	3.82	57.0	14.6	1.74	9.87	28.3	6.5	46

Stress tolerance

Elite F₁ rice hybrids for low-light monsoon areas

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Low light is one of the major constraints to rice production during the wet season (WS). We compared tolerance for low light in selected F₁ rice hybrid combinations (Table 1) with the best low-light-tolerant standard check Swarnaprabha, during the 1990 WS and 1991 WS. The crop was grown in 1.2-m²

field plots at 15- × 10-cm spacing and fertilized with 60 kg N/ha.

Wooden screens were used to create low light (50% sunlight) conditions from 40 d after planting to harvest. Controls were maintained under normal sunlight (about 340 call cm² per d). The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications. The two light treatments were in the main plots and the hybrids in the subplots. Leaf area index (LAI) at flowering, total dry matter (TDM), yield, and harvest index (HI) were recorded at harvest. The photosynthetic rate (P_n) of the boot

leaf at flowering was measured with the LI-6000 Portable Photosynthesis System at near saturated light (above 1,000 μE/m² per s).

P_n, crop photosynthesis (P_n × LAI), TDM, HI, and yield were consistently higher for the hybrids from the pollen parent Vajram, i.e., IR54752 A/Vajram during 1990 and from IR62829 A/Vajram during 1991. The yield, TDM, and HI were also the highest in these hybrids under low light. They were at par or even superior in yield to Swarnaprabha, especially under low light.

Hybrid IR62829 A/Vajram recorded the highest yield during the 1991 WS at